

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CAFFEINE & NICOTINE ADDICTION PATTERN IN YOUNG MALES

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Abstract

Introduction: Caffeine and nicotine are widely consumed legal stimulants with significant public health implications, particularly among youth. To investigate addiction and usage patterns among young males. This study focuses on how these two drugs, nicotine and caffeine alter brain and body functioning. *Methods:* This research encompassed two phases: Phase 1, involved questionnaire data collection and behavioral analysis. In Phase 2, biochemical effects of nicotine and caffeine addiction were assessed via blood sample or biochemical analysis. *Results:* The outcome of this study indicates that fasting blood glucose as well as blood cholesterol for the addicted group (nicotine and caffeine users) was significantly higher than that of the non-addicts. The study analyzed biomarker changes in male individuals with nicotine and caffeine addiction, compared to non-addicts. Nicotine addicts showed significantly higher cholesterol (214.93 mg/dl) and glucose levels (113.20 mg/dl) compared to non-addicts (cholesterol: 107.4 mg/dl, glucose: 87.43 mg/dl). Similarly, caffeine addicts had elevated cholesterol (202.04 mg/dl) and glucose levels (113.14 mg/dl) compared to non-addicts. *Conclusion:* Nicotine and Caffeine consumption by young people has increased dramatically over the last decade, as both the drugs are legal and freely available. Both are addictive and can lead to adverse effects. Nicotine's addictive nature rivals: heroin and cocaine, making quitting challenging, while caffeine addiction, though less severe, also causes withdrawal symptoms but is comparatively easier to overcome.

Index Terms: Blood Glucose, Cholesterol, Biomarkers, Caffeine, Nicotine.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nicotine and Caffeine are legal stimulant drugs that are widely used in many different forms. A legal drug is not necessarily safe or non-addictive, but is freely available, and hence, among the most often abused. As a matter of fact, the legal drugs are by far our greatest addiction problem¹. The most widely used psychoactive stimulant drugs in the world are Nicotine and Caffeine. They stimulate the central nervous system, leading to increased levels of mental and physical energy and alertness, as well as an elevated mood².

Psychoactive substances like nicotine and caffeine raise dopamine levels in the brain's reward or pleasure circuits, which are networks of neurons that produce happy or euphoric experiences^{3,4}. The severe cravings and anxiety that come with drug withdrawal, as well as the difficulties people have staying sober, may be explained by changes in the dopamine system. These changes can also lead to addiction, a condition characterized by compulsive drug seeking and use despite sometimes dire consequences and sometimes resulting in physical dependence^{5,6,7}.

Nicotine and Caffeine consumption by young people has increased dramatically over the last decade^{8,9}. Nicotine and Caffeine are among the most widely used mood-altering drugs in the world¹⁰. Caffeine is commonly consumed orally in various caffeine-containing foods and beverages such as coffee, tea, soft drinks, and chocolate,² and so-called energy drink used nowadays. Nicotine, the primary active constituent of tobacco that leads to addiction,¹¹ is commonly self-administered by cigarette smoking or chewing tobacco products¹⁰. In higher amounts, both the psychoactive stimulants cause many adverse effects that are cause for concern^{12,13,14}.

This study focuses on how two drugs, nicotine and caffeine, change the functioning of the brain and body^{3,4}. Nicotine and Caffeine are the legal stimulants causing the most important public health impact^{15,16}. Both can cause a number of negative effects on the body and brain, ranging from mild symptoms to addiction^{12,13,14}. The aims and objectives of the research are to provide a review on the health effects of stimulants as potential drugs of abuse^{15,16}. To present a review of the biochemical and behavioural mechanisms involved in the addictive nature of nicotine and caffeine^{3,4}. To expand the basic science knowledge base on the biochemical and behavioural effects of nicotine and caffeine, as part of continuing efforts to explain and prevent their use (especially among youth)¹⁷.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

1. Behavioural Study:

It includes the survey conducted on the nicotine and caffeine addicts to determine the behavioural effects of nicotine and caffeine addiction in the addicts^{18,19,20}. A questionnaire was developed with respect to the research topic, under the guidance of a consultant clinical psychologist. The objectives of the study were explained to the participants who signed the consent form, after assurance of confidentiality was provided. Filling of

questionnaire by the selected target audience and analysis of information provided by them was achieved. In the first step literature was reviewed in order to gain maximum knowledge on the health effects of stimulants as potential drugs of abuse^{21,22}. In this phase filling of questionnaire by the selected target audience and behavioral analysis of information provided by them was achieved. All participants were asked to submit written consent for the use of information contained in the questionnaire and for the donation of serum samples. After the filling of questionnaire, the data was statistically analysed using SPSS for Windows version 22.0. Using this statistical approach, a suitable conclusion was reached in the end.

2. Equipment Based Study:

For this study collection of blood samples was required. In this phase analytical study of the collected blood samples is included for the determination of biochemical effects of nicotine and caffeine addiction in the addicts^{18, 19, 20}. Analysis of blood samples using spectrophotometric techniques was done after the collection of blood samples. The study's ethical standards were fulfilled.

3. Serum Biomarkers:

This study evaluates the changes in biomarkers (blood glucose and blood cholesterol) of metabolic syndrome in some nicotine and caffeine users among youth^{23,24}. For our research based on the consequences of nicotine and caffeine addiction we used Microlab 300 (a UV-visible spectrophotometer) to estimate the glucose and cholesterol levels in the addicts as well as the non-addicts, to observe and analyse the differences between the glucose and cholesterol levels of the addicts (i.e., nicotine and caffeine users) compared to the glucose and cholesterol levels of the non-addicts.

4. Participants:

The target audience for the collection of blood samples was the male persons from different educational institutions and working organisations. Forty-five apparently healthy male college students, undergraduate students and fresh graduates, which were divided into three respective groups (15 nicotine addicts, 15 caffeine addicts and 15 non-addicts) were recruited for the study after obtaining their informed consent.

5. Biochemical Study:

A. Collection of Blood Samples: Blood (5ml) was drawn, using disposable syringes by venipuncture from each volunteer and was immediately transferred into Heparin vacutainer tubes. The samples were centrifuged at 2200-3000 rpm for 15 minutes, as soon as possible. Blood plasma was collected in aliquots and stored frozen at -20°C or lower, until required for biochemical analysis.

B. Biochemical Analysis: Blood glucose and blood cholesterol were determined using spectrophotometric techniques.

Procedure for Biochemical Analysis:

Three test tubes were taken. The test tubes were labelled as blank, standard and sample. To these tubes 10 μL water for blank, 10 μL standard for standard and 10 μL sample for sample, along with 1000 μL of reaction solution (reagent) in each test tube were added respectively. Then each test tube was mixed well. The procedure is shown below in tabular form.

Table: Procedure for Determination of Cholesterol and Glucose

	Distilled Water	Reagent	Standard	Sample
BLANK	10 μL	1000 μL	-	-
STANDARD	-	1000 μL	10 μL	-
SAMPLE	-	1000 μL	-	μL

- The instrument was zeroed out by using the blank.
- A calibration curve was constructed using the standard solution.
- The calibration curve was then used to determine the concentration of the unknown solution (i.e., the sample). Sample readings were thus obtained.

C. Statistical Analysis: To compare the estimated means of the parameters, the t-test was employed. After analysis, the data's findings were retrieved.

III. RESULTS

The results obtained from the investigation into changes in biomarkers (blood glucose and blood cholesterol) of metabolic syndrome in addicts (i.e., nicotine and caffeine users) as compared to non-addicts, among male persons from different educational institutions and working organisations are shown in figure 1 and figure 2 respectively.

Results indicate that both the nicotine addicts' cholesterol levels (214.93 ± 28.02 mg/dl) and glucose levels (113.201 ± 11.65 mg/dl) as well as the caffeine addicts' cholesterol levels (202.036 ± 43.57 mg/dl) and glucose levels (113.14 ± 13.275 mg/dl) measures are significantly elevated than those of the non-addicts (cholesterol: 107.4 ± 28.05 mg/dl, glucose: 87.43 ± 9.96 mg/dl) ^{23,24}.

Figure 1: Effect of Nicotine and Caffeine Addiction on Blood Glucose.

Figure 2: Effect of Nicotine and Caffeine Addiction on Blood Cholesterol.

IV. DISCUSSION

Results of this study indicate that fasting blood glucose as well as blood cholesterol for the addicted group (nicotine and caffeine users) was significantly higher than that of the non-addicts^{23,24}. Both nicotine and caffeine cause the release of adrenaline, the "fight or flight" hormone that instructs the body to dump excess glucose into the bloodstream, and thus may aggravate diabetes^{23,25,26}. Nicotine and Caffeine elevate blood cholesterol due

to decreased activity of lipoprotein lipase ²⁴. High blood cholesterol level has been associated with cardiovascular risk. Overall, the results present a pattern that reveals a higher risk of metabolic syndrome ²⁷ among the addicted group (nicotine and caffeine users) as compared to the non-addicts. In clinical research, the tolerance and dependence associated with frequent nicotine or caffeine use may influence study results. This comparative study aimed to explore the distinct characteristics of caffeine and nicotine addiction, including their effects, mechanisms, ^{28, 29} associated health risks, and societal implications ^{30, 31}. By analysing the findings in the context of existing literature, this study contributes to the understanding of the complexities surrounding these two psychoactive substances. The study found that caffeine consumption, within moderate limits, has a relatively higher impact on blood glucose and cholesterol levels in healthy individuals than that of the non-addicts ²⁴. In contrast, nicotine consumption, especially through smoking, poses a more significant risk to metabolic health due to its potential to disrupt glucose homeostasis and negatively affect lipid profiles ²³. Smoking and caffeine separately deteriorate aortic stiffness and wave reflections ^{32, 33}.

Both nicotine and caffeine cause the release of adrenaline, the "fight or flight" hormone that instructs the body to dump excess glucose into the bloodstream, and thus may aggravate diabetes ^{23, 25, 26}. The observed effects of caffeine and nicotine align with established mechanisms of action. Caffeine exhibits the reinforcing and psychomotor effects via increasing dopaminergic system activity through adenosine inhibition. Nicotine gets its reinforcing and psychostimulant effects from blocking dopamine uptake and increasing synaptic dopamine release ^{6, 7}. Caffeine acts as a mild stimulant by antagonizing adenosine receptors, resulting in increased alertness and diminished fatigue perception. On the other hand, nicotine interacts with nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, triggering neurotransmitter release and leading to pleasurable sensations and reward reinforcement ^{28, 29}.

Caffeine withdrawal impairs regular functioning and causes mild to clinically significant distress. The degree of symptoms varies from person to person, but the most prevalent ones include headache, exhaustion, low energy/activity, decreased alertness, drowsiness, low contentment, depression, agitation, and a foggy/unclear headed sensation ^{34, 35}. Consistent with results from past research with non-smokers, nicotine affected cardiovascular response significantly and produced a variety of aversive subjective effects in nonsmokers ^{21, 26}. Both caffeine and nicotine addiction involve dopamine pathways, highlighting their similarities in addictive potential ^{5, 6, 7}. The development of tolerance and desensitization of receptors, which leads to the need for higher doses, is a common phenomenon in addiction ^{35, 36}. While this study confirms the central role of dopamine in both addictions, further research could delve deeper into the molecular mechanisms underlying caffeine and nicotine addiction. Understanding the differential effects of caffeine and nicotine on blood glucose and cholesterol levels is crucial for promoting metabolic health and making informed decisions regarding caffeine and nicotine consumption.

The findings of this study hold relevance for designing targeted interventions. While caffeine addiction might be managed through gradual reduction and lifestyle changes,³⁷ nicotine addiction demands a more comprehensive approach. Nicotine replacement therapies, counselling, and behavioural interventions are crucial components in combating nicotine addiction and reducing its associated health burden³⁸. Ultimately, this comparative study deepens the understanding of caffeine and nicotine addiction by examining their effects, mechanisms, health risks, and societal implications. The findings underscore the shared neural pathways underpinning addiction while highlighting the marked divergence in their health impacts. By recognizing these distinctions, policymakers, healthcare professionals, and individuals can better address the challenges posed by caffeine and nicotine addiction, ultimately promoting healthier behaviours and improved public health outcomes. Further research could explore the potential long-term effects of caffeine and nicotine consumption on various demographic groups, providing a more comprehensive understanding of their addictive potential.

V. CONCLUSION

Nicotine and Caffeine are two of the most abused drugs in various forms. While coffee is consumed by people as an energy drink that contains caffeine, the most popular source of nicotine intake is cigarette. Nicotine and Caffeine consumption by young people has increased dramatically over the last decade, as both the drugs are legal and freely available. Both nicotine and caffeine are stimulants. Both increase alertness and concentration and are **addictive**. In higher amounts, both the psychoactive stimulants cause many adverse effects that are cause for concern. Nicotine is a very addictive drug. Researchers have suggested that it is as addictive as heroin or cocaine. Your body will require more nicotine as a tolerance grows in order to experience its effects. Once a person becomes addicted, it will be difficult to quit. It is also possible to become addicted to caffeine. Addiction to caffeine, however, carries far less risk. However, using caffeinated items on a daily basis may cause negative physical repercussions. Additionally, if someone quits taking caffeine after being addicted, they will experience withdrawal symptoms. But quitting caffeine addiction is not as difficult as overcoming a nicotine addiction.

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